

YOUNG PEOPLE LIVE SUSTAINABLY

Prepared by: Ariana Sadiku, Ana Dragic, Md Fahim Harun

Market analysis with focus on customers

Engaging children and young people (ages 8-24) of Utrecht with low-income backgrounds in sustainable development, ensuring their ideas are considered by policymakers.

Target groups	
Primary target group	Secondary target group
Children and young people with low income	Policymakers
Specific subgroups	Specific subgroups
Children 8-12 years of age	Local government officials National policymakers
Teenagers 13-17 years of age	
Young adults 18-24 years of age	

Primary target groups					
Specific subgroups	Background	Interests and habits	Motivation and Influences	Sustainability awareness	Challenges and barriers
Children 8-12 years of age	*Primary and early secondary school boys and girls living in urban and rural areas of Utrecht, from families with low income.	*Love watching and playing sports, outdoor activities like biking, skateboarding, climbing trees. *Enjoy video	*They are mostly influenced by parents or other family members *Teachers and school activities *Friends and peer groups	*Their awareness is often practical not theoretical *They perform some basic sustainable practises like turning off lights to save money, saving water, using bikes, not throwing trash	*Difficulties in understanding the concept and the importance of sustainability for the society *In families with low income struggling with

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Developing cognitive abilities *Beginning to understand cause and effect *Curious to learn through hands- on experiences 	<p>games like minecraft, fortnite popular across all genders, they play competitive, creative, socializing and storytelling video games.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Interested in do it yourself and mechanical activities and projects like building with recycled materials, fixing old toys or electronics *Love challenges and competitions *Love pets and animals in general *Enjoy watching cartoons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Role models in sports, art, gaming and entertainment *Motivated by fun, competitive and rewarding activities 	<p>in the environment, sharing food and toys with friends, reusing things out of necessity not being aware of environmental and social benefits.</p>	<p>housing or food those take priority over "green choices".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Children from families with low income are less exposed to eco-products or sustainability campaigns which often target wealthier audiences. *Sustainability is to abstract for them and they feel that it should be more of older people or powerful people issue. *At this age they are more concerned with school and recreative activities (playing) rather than being responsible for the future.
<p>Teenagers 13-17 years of age</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *In general teenagers 13-17 years of age are secondary (middle) school students, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Mobile phones are their main tool for connection and entertainment. *Love watching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *A strong desire to belong and connect with others, be part of group activities like sports, music, or online communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Their awareness for sustainable development is growing but still practical *Many are aware of basic sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustainability is often seen as a luxury issue and out of reach like organic food, expensive eco-products. *Lack of access to green

	<p>developing strong sense of resilience, community and loyalty to family and friends. *May experience higher level of stress due to financial insecurity or family responsibilities. *Many of them see education as a key to upward mobility. *Capable of big impact when involved in initiatives that feel relevant to their lives.</p>	<p>and creating contents in social media channels like youtube, tik- tok, instagram, snapchat. *They develop a strong interest in looking good and expressing identity, even with limited budgets. Many express themselves through art, music, writing. Interest in sports like football, cycling, basketball etc.</p>	<p>*Many teens are motivated by the need to escape everyday stress at home and school. *They are also motivated by the need to make their families proud especially when parents have limited opportunities. *They are driven by the idea of " making it" or breaking the cycles of poverty. *Friends have a major influence, they follow what is popular among their group *Influencers, youtubers, tiktok creators shape their language, goals and self-image. *They are highly motivated by stories of people who become successful from humble beginnings *A trusted adult whether a coach, mentor or teacher can</p>	<p>issues: recycling, climate change, plastic pollution, saving energy. *Their understanding tends to be experienced- based rather than theoretical or academic. *They care about clean air, animal welfare, climate change. *Subjects like science, geography introduces them to environmental topics. *News coverage of climate events like flods, heatwaves makes issues feel real and local.</p>	<p>spaces, eco-education programs or sustainable alternatives. *Frustration or skepticism because they feel that the system is unfair, "why should we care when big companies pollute the most?" *Information gaps are also a barrier-schools may not provide in- depth education about sustaiability. *Sustainability topics may feel abstract or to global. *They feel unheard or undervalued in society and think that their ideas wont matter.</p>
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			be a great influence or motivator		
<i>Young adults 18-24 years of age</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Many are in transition phases: finishing secondary school or attending Intermediate Vocational Education which is more common among young people from low income families as that leads directly to work *Often resilient and resourceful especially in navigating systems with limited support *They may face housing insecurity and some take on adult responsibilities early like contributing to rent. *Financial stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *They enjoy spending time in public spaces like parks, shopping areas, cafes or community centers. *They are big consumers of music *Youtube, tiktok, instagram, snapchat are popular platforms among them. *Online and console gaming is a common hobby. *They show interest in team sports(football, basketball), fitness and gym culture. *Interest in street wear, sneakers and branded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *They are motivated by a strong desire to earn money and be independent from their parents or social welfare *Motivated to support their parents or siblings as success is often seen as a family achievement, not just personal. *Want to prove themselves to family and society. *Motivated by the need to fit in or be respected by peers. *They are influenced by peers and friends, social media and influencers, family is also a big influence. *Coaches, youth workers, local leaders who understand their situation and offer real talk are highly respected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Most are aware of basic sustainability issues like: climate change, plastic waste, recycling, energy use but the depth of understanding can vary. *They care about the environment but may not prioritize it if it conflicts with affordability *There is A growing awareness of climate justice the idea that environmental problems also impact low-income communities more. *They already perform some sustainable habits like recycle, use bikes or public transport, avoid food waste or share with friends/family etc. These action are often driven by cost rather than environmental goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustainable choices are often more expensive. *Lack of tailored messaging as campaigns don't always feel relatable or speak their language. *They may feel their individual actions don't matter if big corporation aren't changing *Some live in neighborhoods with fewer green spaces, recycling bins or community gardens. *Limited exposure to in-depth sustainability education *Lack of platforms or support system- schools *Workplaces or neighborhoods may not have sustainability-focused groups where young people can share ideas. *Lack of mentorship or guidance from community leaders or

	is a constant pressure.	clothing even on a tight budget. *Constant phone use, often multitasking between apps. *Prefer cheap, fast and accessible food. *They engage with activism with practical topics like equality, racism, mental health and climate change			educators on how to start discussions or get involved in sustainability *Overload of information- constantly seeing devastating news about the environment can lead to feeling hopeless and apathy
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Approach strategies				
Children 8-12 years of age	Educational and Interactive Programs	Creative Campaigns	Digital Engagement	Implementation to Influence Policymakers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustainability Workshops *Create fun, hands-on workshops focused on simple sustainable practices *School partnerships- Collaborate with local schools to integrate sustainability topics into curriculum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Art and craft projects involving Sustainability-themed posters, drawings etc *Storytelling and Role-playing which include stories to help children understand the importance of sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Interactive Mobile Games or Apps which include simple, educational mobile apps or games that help children understand sustainability concepts while having fun *Digital Storytelling- Create digital stories or cartoons on sustainability issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Involve children in projects like "Green Ambassador Program" where they share their art and ideas with local councils, creating a platform for their voices to be heard
Teenagers 13-17 years of age	Social Media and Peer Influence	Hackathons and Competitions	Workshops and Skill Development	Implementation to Influence Policymakers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Youth-Led Initiatives aiming to empower teenagers to design and lead their own sustainability campaigns *Social Media Activism that encourages teenagers to use social media platforms (Instagram, TikTok, etc.) to share sustainability tips and advocate for environmental policies *Influencer Partnerships which involves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustainability Challenges: Organize "green" innovation challenges or hackathons where teenagers can submit ideas for sustainable products, services, or community projects. *Youth Sustainability Awards: Host an annual competition where teenagers can submit projects, like creating sustainable solutions or green startups, with the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Career-Oriented Sustainability Workshops that involves workshops that connect sustainability with career options (e.g., sustainable business practices, green technologies, and urban planning) and introduction to potential career paths in sustainability fields *Sustainability Literacy Programs: Teach teenagers how to understand sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Form "Teen Sustainability Councils" where teenagers present their findings, ideas, and campaigns to local government representatives, advocating for changes in their communities (e.g., waste management improvements or youth engagement in environmental policies).

	<p>collaboration with local influencers or social media personalities who share sustainable practices and ideas, making sustainability trendy and accessible to teenagers</p> <p>*Sustainable Fashion Campaigns: Since many teenagers are interested in fashion, launch a campaign around sustainable fashion choices, like thrift shopping, upcycling old clothes, or supporting eco-friendly brands</p>	<p>chance to have their work presented to city officials or local policymakers</p>	<p>data (e.g., carbon footprints, recycling rates) and turn it into actionable proposals for local policy improvements</p> <p>*DIY and Upcycling Projects through which teenagers can learn how to repurpose old clothes, accessories, or household items into new products</p>	
	Accessible Sustainability for All	Workshops, Panels, and Dialogues	Green Entrepreneurship	Implementation to Influence Policymakers
Young adults 18-24 years of age	<p>*Offer practical, affordable solutions that young adults can incorporate into their lives. For instance, promote second-hand goods, energy-saving tips, or how to start a small vegetable garden at home. Focus on low-cost options that don't require a financial commitment but still make a positive</p>	<p>*Sustainability Dialogues and Policy Panels: Organize panel discussions or workshops on local sustainability issues, inviting experts, youth activists, and local government representatives. This gives young adults a chance to interact directly with policymakers, share their views, and discuss actionable solutions.</p>	<p>*Support for Startups: Encourage and support young adults in starting sustainable businesses, such as eco-friendly products, sustainable fashion, or renewable energy solutions. Provide mentorship, funding opportunities and networking.</p> <p>*Idea Incubators: Create incubator programs for</p>	<p>Encourage young adults to form "Green Policy Advocacy Groups" where they can work together to research and propose policy solutions to local government (e.g., introducing green public transportation or expanding green spaces in low-income neighborhoods).</p> <p>Involve young adults in local town hall meetings, where</p>

	<p>environmental impact</p> <p>*Student Discounts or Collaborations with Local Businesses which requires partnering with local businesses or sustainable brands to offer discounts for students or young adults, making it easier for them to access eco-friendly products</p>	<p>*Policy Advocacy Training: Offer workshops on how to effectively advocate for sustainability policies, how to write policy briefs, and how to engage in local government decision-making processes.</p>	<p>young adults to develop innovative sustainability solutions, with the potential to pitch ideas to local government or businesses for funding and implementation.</p>	<p>they can present their ideas directly to policymakers</p>
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Local Comparable campaigns

Identifying similar campaigns to understand who else is active, what strategies are working to engage youth in sustainability and what are the gaps we can fill with our young people live sustainably campaign

Campaign name	Target group	Main Methods/Tools	Strengths	Gaps
AllOne	Youth and young adults	Storytelling through art, music, spoken word Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Engagement methods are creative and involve fun activities to make social issues approachable *Projects involve people of diverse backgrounds including refugees *They involve the community in building projects rather than making projects for them *Their projects focus on social well-being, connection etc , targeting invisible issues like loneliness or exclusion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Ecological sustainability and issues like climate change, green habits are rarely addressed *Weak connection between youth and policymakers *The activities mostly take place outside schools missing the opportunity to work through education channels. *Website and online tools are too basic, lacking interactivity. Projects most of the time are short-term which makes the results less sustainable.
Utrecht4GlobalGoals	Schools and young activists	Lessons, exhibitions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Creative educational materials to introduce students to the sustainable development goals *Students from different educational backgrounds organize conferences on social and green sustainability Global challenges are treated through local actions helping students understand the relevance of SDGs within their own communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *While they provide physical materials and organize events, digital engagement platforms lack interactivity *Current initiatives do not explicitly connect students with policymakers, missing the opportunity for youth to participate in policy discussions *Programs like YOUTH can face

			<p>*It works closely with schools and educators to tailor programs that fit specific educational context</p>	<p>challenges while trying to grow or replicate across more schools because of the absence of a structured framework</p> <p>*There is a lack of clear evaluation methods to assess the effectiveness of their educational programs in achieving learning outcomes related to SDGs</p>
Zin in Actie	Young adults (19-30)	Community expeditions, Games nights	<p>*initiated and organized by young adults aged 18–30 from Utrecht North- East. This peer-led approach fosters ownership and relevance among participants</p> <p>*The group organizes a variety of activities, including clothing swaps, game nights, film screenings, and neighborhood expeditions this way ensuring capturing a wider range of interests</p> <p>*Through neighborhood expeditions, participants discover existing local initiatives and identify opportunities to contribute, enhancing their connection to the community</p>	<p>*The initiative currently has a minimal online footprint, with limited use of social media platforms and digital tools to engage a broader audience or document activities</p> <p>*There is no explicit mention of collaborations with local authorities or efforts to influence policy, which could enhance the impact of their community initiatives</p> <p>*While the group engages in various community events, there is a lack of emphasis on environmental sustainability or climate-related projects</p> <p>*Zin in Actie operates independently of schools or educational programs</p>
Jong Voor Utrecht	13–30 young volunteers	Volunteering projects	<p>*Offers young people aged 13 to 30 opportunities to make a positive impact in their city, fostering a sense</p>	<p>*The initiative currently has a minimal digital footprint, which may hinder its ability to reach</p>

		Matchmaking platform	<p>of agency and community involvement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *The program provides a variety of volunteering options, allowing participants to choose roles that align with their interests and skills *By engaging in volunteer work, participants can discover their strengths, develop new skills, and gain valuable experiences that contribute to their personal growth. *Jong Voor Utrecht emphasizes the importance of young people in creating a vibrant volunteer community, encouraging collaboration and mutual support among participants 	<p>and engage a broader audience of young people</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *There is limited information on structured programs or pathways for participants, which could provide clearer guidance and progression opportunities for volunteers *Insufficient Visibility of Impact *There appears to be a lack of formal partnerships with schools or educational programs
EcologiCo	University students	Green projects Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Empowers students to conceptualize and execute various sustainability initiatives. Notable projects include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taste Before You Waste: A campaign aimed at reducing food waste. Green Week: An event series focused on environmental awareness. Campus Gardening: Maintaining a garden to promote local food production and biodiversity Educational Events: Organizing lectures, workshops, film nights, and discussions on sustainability topics *EcologiCo collaborates with academic programs and community projects, such as partnering with Energie U to promote energy-saving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *EcologiCo's digital presence is minimal, which may hinder outreach and engagement with a broader audience *there is no explicit mention of collaborations with policymakers or efforts to influence sustainability policies at the municipal or university level. *Projects appear to be localized, with limited information on efforts to scale successful initiatives beyond the UCU campus *Although EcologiCo offers practical experiences, there is no clear indication of integration with UCU's academic curriculum

			practices among students and local residents	to reinforce sustainability education
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Suggestions and Marketing campaign ideas

One of the gaps that was more frequent among the initiatives was lack of school integration, you also mentioned it as one of the your problems.

Since you are partnered with Utrecht4GlobalGoals, which works with schools and educators, you can collaborate to deliver your ideas in sustainability, promote your work and engage more students. Through your marketing campaign you should focus in filling the gaps there are amongst the local initiatives to make meaningful and fruitful difference.

AllOne, which is one of your partners lacks the handling of ecological issues while focusing more in social issues. When working together try complementing each other to deliver to capture a wider range of sustainability-related matters.

Another disadvantage encountered in the activities of local initiatives was a poor online footprint. Almost all initiatives's online platforms lacked creativity at some degree and most importantly interactivity.

Online platforms, if used properly can set bridges between young people and policymakers, and offer an environment they can constantly be together.

I would suggest that the ethicschool website changed into a more creative and fun place to visit, as it is more filled with work presentation and what is offered in text form. Some pictures of people especially young people working around your initiatives would be good and also the presentation of your activities, which from what I see is not in deficit, in a more creative way would make your page more attractive. Try exposing your work through pictures and images of your activities and make a section for participants to leave their impressions.

One of the problems the campaign should address is the gap between young people and policymakers. The latter should be included in most of the activities with young people especially those that include the presentation of their ideas on sustainability.

Here are some marketing campaign ideas inspired by the gaps and strengths of the local initiatives studied:

*** Sustainability School Kit + Ambassadors**

Create a fun and accessible Sustainability Starter Kit for schools with: DIY projects (e.g., recycled fashion, upcycled art), challenges (e.g., “Zero-Waste Day” or “Greenest Class”), a rotating Youth Ambassador Program where students host monthly sustainability meetups.

***Interactive digital platform-** It can be an app or microsite (it can be named Ecosnap) where teens and young adults can log sustainable actions for points, you can host monthly challenges and show leaderboards by school or neighborhood and invite policymakers to respond to top voted ideas

***A Youth & Policy Debate Series (Sustain Mic)-** It can be livestreams debates where different topics and issues related to sustainability. Policymakers can share their goals and challenges while asking young people to share solution ideas.

***Social media campaign** (I would highly suggest tiktok) and street poster campaign where young people can finish sentences like "If i was to decide, I would. " these video messages should tag local leaders and schools when posted

The most important things to have in mind when designing a marketing campaign are:

Partnerships - Co-brand some actions with EcologiCo, AllOne or Utrecht4GlobalGoals

Visual identity and original slogans- Use youth-drawn or youth-designed graphics

Make it like a movement and not a one-time event.